

EGN Method for NLI Estimation in Digital Subcarrier Allocation for Horseshoe Networks

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Abstract—Using a fast and accurate EGN model in digital subcarrier-based communication, we address the NLI noise in a horseshoe network. This method offers a computationally cheap simulation environment with the advantage of being scalable to different DWDM configurations, offering a robust solution for low-complexity networks.

Index Terms—Nonlinear Interference Noise, DSCM, EGN, DWDM, horseshoe network, SSFM, Add/Drop, Monte-Carlo.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the current state for data traffic in optical networks is becoming more demanding, with a dire need to improve the technology available to meet the increasing data demand. Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM) has been shown over the last few years to be a robust answer to this challenge, even in a short-reach scenario, as it uses optical aggregation to supply end-users [1]. Furthermore, the use of spectrally densely packed subcarriers (SCs) reduces the impact of common impairments, such as chromatic dispersion, and enables spectral efficiency, flexible bandwidth allocation, and overall flexibility in implementation and upgradability of the system. This work employs the Enhanced Gaussian Noise (EGN) model [2] to quantify Nonlinear Interference (NLI) noise within a short-reach optical communication system, focusing on several critical features: (i) the possibility to integrate SCs within the simulation framework, (ii) account for Optical Add/Drop Multiplexing (OADM) for SC-based WDM channels, (iii) the ability to perform accurate NLI estimations in the case of a real network scenario (horseshoe) and (iv) provide insights on its scalability in terms of computational cost and extent of the simulation. Furthermore, the standard EGN model accounts for a full bandwidth integration simulation and, for the sake of computational efficiency and scalability, we apply standard Monte-Carlo (MC) techniques to solve the multi-dimensional integrals within the EGN model, thus improving its speed to converge to the solution [3]. Although these methods are well established within the literature, moving onward we will refer to this approach as MC-EGN. This method offers a low-computation simulation environment in the spectral domain, scalable to different Dense Wavelength Division multiplexing (DWDM) configurations, and offers a robust solution for low-complexity network scenarios, while accounting for all NLI noise components for every SC considered, without loss of accuracy.

II. SIMULATION FRAMEWORK AND RESULTS

The MC-EGN model operates under specific assumptions and constraints as per the physical interpretation of the results. To assess its accuracy and relevance, a common technique is to compare its results against the ones produced by other well-known and established methods in the literature, namely, with the Split-Step Fourier Method (SSFM), to solve the Manakov equation in the time-domain, and the Gaussian Noise model (GN). Likewise, the key parameters and assumptions provided by this work can be found in Table I and they can be interpreted across all methods mentioned in this article.

TABLE I
KEY SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	Units
α	0.22	dB/km
γ	1.30	$W^{-1} \cdot km^{-1}$
GVD	21.30	ps^2/km
MC samples	10^6	points
Optical Band	1550	nm
Symbol Rate	4	GBd
Pulse Shape	Nyquist	–
Modulation	DP-16QAM	–

First, we compare the results for two different reach scenarios (10 km and 100 km) across all three methods (SSFM, GN and MC-EGN) which are displayed in Fig. 1. Considering the DSCM scenario with 4 GBd per SC, Four-wave Mixing (FWM) is dominant over other Kerr-effects such as Self-phase Modulation (SPM) or Cross-phase Modulation (XPM). Because of this, the performance of the GN model is less accurate than MC-EGN when compared with the golden standard of SSFM. Moreover, since FWM is more relevant within the first spans with respect to XPM/SPM, there is a good match between MC-EGN and SSFM for all spans.

Based on the physical layer scenario presented in Table I, a simulation was carried out where we added, after 5 spans, 2 SCs at the edges of the transmission bandwidth, to the initial 3 SCs. The results are reported in Fig. 2. The estimation of the NLI attained with the MC-EGN model shows a good match and accuracy with respect to SSFM. Note that, additionally, it is also presented the NLI versus span length curves obtained by purely transmitting 3 SCs and 5 SCs within the full length of the simulation. The correspondence between these trends and the one that may be observed for the addition of new SCs scenario confirms the ability of our proposed approximation

Fig. 1. Comparison of different modeling tools (SSFM, GN and MC-EGN) estimated NLI applied to a multi-span fiber link, for a dual-polarization 16QAM transmission, at 4 GBd rate and comprising 21 DSCs.

of the EGN to accommodate additional SCs, even within the same simulation run, showing the flexibility and adaptability of these methods, without sacrificing unexpected computational power.

Fig. 2. MC-EGN performance results when adding 2 SCs at the edge of a 3 SCs transmission at the 5th span, as shown by the inset. This simulation was carried out to estimate NLI in case of a multi-span fiber link, for a dual-polarization 16QAM transmission, at 4 GBd rate and with a span length of 100 km. Note that all EGN corrections are calculated, according to [2]: i.e. SCI, XCI, MCI terms.

In Fig. 3, we consider the transmission of 16 SCs in the depicted horseshoe network scenario (see insets in Fig. 3). Here, the MC-EGN is applied for NLI estimation in comparison with the standard SSFM. The results attained show the agreement between the two models for different two SCs under test. Moreover, the results ultimately report that MC-EGN is resilient in dealing with non-uniform power distribution among subcarriers, since it shows a good match between MC-EGN and SSFM for the outer SC16 and the central SC1, where SC16 was digitally pre-emphasized. Finally, this

Fig. 3. SSFM and MC-EGN simulation of 16 SCs (spectrum shown in bottom-right inset) in a horseshoe network (depicted in top-left inset). The attained total NLI was recorded for both the central SC1 and the outer SC16.

technique shows potential to be tested in the future with more complex network topology scenarios, pushing our knowledge on NLI noise estimation techniques and allowing for the accommodation of more complex signal modulation scenarios such as DSCM.

III. CONCLUSION

This research shows the already well-established agreement between different modeling tools, namely, the SSFM and the MC-EGN model. The results obtained for the SC Add scenario show the promising adaptable framework that the MC-EGN model can provide in a DSCM scenario for access-metro network topologies. Furthermore, it is shown that MC-EGN can be applied to a horseshoe network, where OADMs play a crucial role in providing service to end-users, thus highlighting the potential of this tool to account accurately for channel impairments towards a real network scenario, at a much less computational cost than the one needed to run the full SSFM simulation for this particular case. Lastly, according to our simulations, this method proved to be scalable within the framework of densely packed SCs multiplexing, even when SCs are digitally pre-emphasized, showcasing an opportunity to implement these tools for network performance assessment in close-to-realtime scenarios.

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